

The Sanctuary of Demeter at Dion

By Dafni MaikidouPoutrino, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Macedonian Religions, Greece, Religious Group, Greek Mystery Cults, Macedonia, Greek Religions, Dion, Religious Place, Macedonia

The sanctuary of Demeter is the most ancient sanctuary testified at Dion. It was located outside the city, at the "sacred area", where all sanctuaries were constructed. The location is just outside the city walls, to the south of the city, to the north of the (later) sanctuary of Asklepios and to the west of the sanctuary of Zeus Hypsistos. It is important to stress out that the cult of Demeter presents a long continuity through time, from the late Archaic period till late antiquity, with many consequent architectural phases of construction.

Date Range: 500 BCE - 300 CE

Region: Dion-Macedonia

Region tags: Greece, Northern Greece, Macedonia

The city of Dion is mentioned by Thucydides for the first time, who doesn't provide any information about the city except its place under mountain Olympus. Towards the end of the 5th century Dion became an important city, when the king of Macedonians Archelaos (413-399 BC) organized the "Olympia", festivities dedicated to the nine Muses and on Zeus. Still nothing is known for the previous phases of the city. Archaeological evidence can hardly attribute some finds to a 5th century BCE phase. The earliest monument preserved in the city is indeed the late archaic sanctuary of Demeter.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Pingiatoglou, S. 2015. Διον, το ιερό της Δήμητρος. University Studio Press.
- Source 2: Pingiatoglou, S. 2005. Διον, το ιερό της Δήμητρος: οι λύχνοι. University Studio Press.
- Source 3: Pandermalis, D. 1997. Δίον: Αρχαιολογικός χώρος και Μουσείο. Αδάμ.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=979
- Source 1 Description: Official website of the Ministry of Culture
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.archaiologia.gr/blog/issue/%CE%B4%CE%AF%CE%BF%CE%BD-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CE%B9%CE%B5%CF%81%CF%8C-%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%82-%CE%B4%CE%AE%CE%BC%CE%B7%CF%84%CF%81%CE%B1%CF%82/>
- Source 2 Description: Archaeology Online Journal
- Source 3 URL: <http://dion-excavation.web.auth.gr/-/index.php/anaskafiko-ergo/arxaiologikos-xoros/iera>
- Source 3 Description: Official site of the Academic Excavation

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1973-1985

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Academic Excavation from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki under the direction of D. Pandermalis

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest
- Body of water (as distinct from source)
- Marsh or bog

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary is situated just outside the city walls, in the area where all sanctuaries were situated.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is not inside the urban grid but it is just outside the city in close relation to the city walls.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The oldest evidence is provided by two temples perhaps of the "megaron" type. Both of them were destroyed by latter building which includes temples and altars, an "eschara" for the sacrifices, the "building with the wells", a stoa, an oikos with a table of offerings. All these buildings changed through the centuries as some buildings were destroyed and others were rebuilt.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: It is a single sanctuary with many buildings part of a large area with sacred spaces dedicated to many different gods.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The structures lasted for many centuries, when they were destroyed due to fires or earthquakes these buildings were rebuilt.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The structures lasted for many centuries, when they were destroyed due to fires or earthquakes these buildings were rebuilt.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The structures lasted for many centuries, when they were destroyed due to fires or earthquakes these buildings were rebuilt.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Either burned or collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Demeter and her daughter Persephone

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Perhaps all the above

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary included two temples with their altars, that are the centre of the cult, and other buildings around, such as a stoa, an oikos, an eschara.

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Only the foundation of the buildings have been preserved.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Square meters: 2580

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Probably

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: The building would have the shape of a Greek temple, therefore the pediment, the columns, the architectural features in general, would also be the decoration of the building.

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:
– Yes

Notes: Demeter and Persephone would be present at the decoration of the building.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Field doesn't know

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Probably

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: A head of Demeter that was found in the sanctuary is considered cultic.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Statues of Demeter, Aphrodite, Eros, Muses, Nemesis have been found at the sanctuary.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Statues of women dressed with peplos have been found at the sanctuary.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Very few reliefs.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there paintings present:
– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– No

↳ Other type of decoration:
– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Statues of Demeter and other gods, mainly Aphrodite, Eros, Nemesis and Demeter's daughter.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Statues representing humans, especially female figures, have been found during the excavations of the sanctuary.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes, even though mystic rites might had taken place in that sanctuary.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: The statue would be inside the temple and perhaps visible only in some specific times of the year.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: There was an eschara for offerings and perhaps libations and there was a building with wells which architectonically has not been fully understood.

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: The altar would host these offerings.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Probably yes, as in analogous sanctuaries in the Greek world.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Especially the presence of the lamps shows that except for the practical use, they would serve for nocturnal or other rites.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Through rites, prayers, offerings.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: These would be hosted at the altar.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: They are not mandatory but they would create a relation of reciprocity between the divine figure and the humans.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary had a long history of at least 7 centuries, thus it has been repaired and restored periodically many times.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Probably annually

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Field doesn't know

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The specific festivities would need specific buildings, places and space.

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Field doesn't know

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Probably once per year there would be the festival (of Thesmophoria?) but as other deities were also worshiped there - as the statues of Aphrodite show - perhaps there were more than one festivities and other rites in a yearly basis.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Probably there would be people - priest, neokoroï, or others - that would have duties and roles inside the sanctuary and its rites.

- ↳ Present full time
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Present part time
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Sanctuary of Demeter at Dion, Pandermalis, Dimitrios. Δίον. Η Ανακάλυψη. Αδάμ, n.d..

Reference: The Sanctuary of Demeter at Dion, Pingiatoglou, Semeli. Το Ιερό Της Δήμητρος. Thessaloniki: University Studio Press, 2015.

Reference: The Sanctuary of Demeter at Dion, Pingiatoglou, Semelo. Το Ιερό Της Δήμητρος. Οι Λύχνοι. Thessaloniki: University Studio Press, 2005.

Reference: The Sanctuary of Demeter at Dion, Pingiatoglou, Semeli. "Cults of Female Deities at Dion". *Kernos* 23 (January 1, 2010): 179-92.